

Relativistic Harmonic Oscillator and the Klein Gordon Equation

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The Klein Gordon equation for the harmonic oscillator may be written as $(E - .5kx^2)^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ ((1)) where m_0 is the rest mass and p the relativistic momentum. In the literature, it is argued that the resulting x^4 term dominates for large x and prevents the Klein Gordon equation from being solved for bound states. As a result, it is replaced with an equation of the form: $(E^2 - m_0^2) = (p - im\omega x)(p + im\omega x)$ ((2)) where $p = -i\hbar d/dx$ in one dimension which may be solved exactly. Recently, the authors of (1) have used perturbation theory to calculate energy changes to ((1)) by using $-.5V^2 - e^2 + 2eV$ as a perturbative potential where $V = .5kx^2$ and $E = e + m_0$. They utilise the unperturbed wavefunction $\exp(-ax^2)$ so large x^4 values are damped. Their results are close to the exact calculations of ((2)) for the case of $k=1$ and $m=1$. In this note, we argue that for an oscillator there are classical turning points at which the quantum average kinetic energy $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W$ should be zero and small nearby even if the average kinetic energy near $x=0$ corresponds to relativistic momenta. Thus, it is argued there are different spatial regions, each with its own quantum equation. The Schrodinger equation may be applied to regions near the classical turning point moving to infinite. In such a case, there is no issue with an x^4 term. Near $x=0$, the full Klein Gordon equation ((1)) may be applied. There are questions of then matching the two sets of solutions. In this note, we attempt to investigate this scenario and compare results with those of (1) and (2). (1) and (2) suggest similar relativistic corrections to the nonrelativistic ground state oscillator energy of more than 20%. In this note, we suggest a smaller value.

Results from the literature

We consider here two treatments of the relativistic oscillator (1) and (2). In both cases, it is agreed there is no bound state solution for ((1)) (the Klein Gordon equation) because of the behaviour of x^4 for large x . In (1), a perturbation method is used with the perturbation taken from ((1)) i.e.

$V_p = -.5V^2 - e^2 + 2eV$ where $V = .5kx^2$ and $E = e + m_0$ and the unperturbed equation being:

$$.5 p^2 + V + V_p = e \quad ((2a))$$

The authors of (1) use $m=1$, $k=1$ and $(3.14)^{-.25} \exp(-.5x^2)$ as the unperturbed ground state wavefunction (assume $e \ll m_0$ which seems like a nonrelativistic situation). Their result for the ground state is:

egs correction = $-3/32$ and $egs = .5$ i.e. $\hbar \omega (n + .5)$ with $n=0$ and $w=1$ Note $E_{gs} = e_{gs} + m_0 = 1.5$ for $m_0=1$

In (2), the Klein Gordon equation is replaced with:

$$(E^2 - m^2) = (p - imwx)(p + imw) \quad ((2))$$

It may be noted $imwx$ is equivalent to a ground state flux for a nonrelativistic oscillator i.e. $-i \frac{d}{dx} W / W$. In quantum mechanics, there seems to be two velocities, one associated with $1/2m \langle p^2 \rangle$ quantum average $\Rightarrow -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W$ and one with $-i \frac{d}{dx} W / W$. In general, the square of the latter does not equal the former. For the ground state nonrelativistic oscillator, however:

$$\frac{d}{dx} (-i \frac{d}{dx} W / W) = iwm \quad \text{and}$$

$$iwm + (-i \frac{d}{dx} W / W)^2 + V(x) = E$$

so the two velocities are very similar. Interestingly for the ground state nonrelativistic oscillator, the wavefunction is proportional to $\exp(-ax^2)$ and its Fourier transform to $\exp(-bp^2)$, which matches classical statistical mechanics. For the relativistic case, however, things are more complicated.

((2)) may be solved exactly and it is noted that the results coincide with the nonrelativistic case in the nonrelativistic limit. This is not surprising because $(E^2 - m^2) = 2m_0 e$ in the nonrelativistic situation and ((2)) becomes the exact nonrelativistic equation. The results (taken from (2)) for the energy are:

$$e(n) = (n + .5)w - .5 (n + .5)^2 w^2/m \quad \text{with } w = \sqrt{k/m}$$

For $w=1$, $m=1$ and $n=0$ one finds e_0 correction $= -1/8 = -4/32$ which differs from $-3/32$ given in (1), although the two are similar. The unperturbed ground state energy is $.5$ so $-1/8$ is a substantial correction (over 20%).

Different Quantum Equations for Different Regions?

In special relativity, one assigns $p = \text{momentum} = mv / \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2}$ ((2b)). If velocity v is much smaller than c (the speed of light), $p = mv$ which is the nonrelativistic result. This p will change due to a force according to Newton's law. If one is in a region for which a small velocity changes slowly, it seems this should be a nonrelativistic region. Later, the force may accelerate the particle to relativistic velocities, but this should not affect the calculation in the region in which the particle is moving slowly and being accelerated slowly. Similarly, quantum mechanics seems to be based on energy equations. For the nonrelativistic case, one uses $KE(\text{quantum average})(x) + V(x) = E$ where:

$$KE(\text{quantum average})(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W \quad ((3))$$

Here one considers an unusual average of plane wave states $\exp(ipx)$ i.e.

$$KE(\text{quantum average})(x) = (\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \int \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } p \int \exp(ipx)) \quad ((4))$$

In a region where $KE(\text{quantum average})(x)$ is nonrelativistic, it seems one should be able to apply the Schrodinger equation. If the particle gains relativistic speeds in another region, the Klein Gordon may be applied there. Thus, we argue that it seems one apply different quantum equations to different regions. It should be noted that in the relativistic region, equations ((3)) and ((4)) hold, but p refers now to the relativistic momentum.

Instead of using ((2a)) in the region about $x=0$, we retain all linear terms in V i.e.:

$$p^2 + m^2 = E^2 - 2EV \quad ((5))$$

The ground state solution of this equation is a Gaussian $\exp(-ax^2)$ where:

$$E^2 - m^2 = -2a \quad \text{and} \quad Ek = 4a^2 \quad \text{or} \quad (E^2 - m^2) = Ek \quad ((6))$$

For $m=1$ and $k=1$ as used in ((1)), we find that E_{gs} is about 1.49 or $egs=.49$ which almost the same as the nonrelativistic result.

The term V^2 may be taken as a perturbation near $x=0$ using:

$$\text{Correction in } egs = \text{integral about } x=0 \text{ to turning points } dx \quad W^2 V^2$$

where $W = B \exp(-ax^2)$ $B = \text{normalization factor}$

For the case of $m=1$ and $k=1$ $W = B \exp(-ax^2)$ where a is about .62 from ((6)) and the perturbation $V^2 = (.5x^2)^2$

As an approximation, we use $W = B \exp(-.5x^2)$ from (1) and find, using the results from (1) and integrating from minus infinite to infinite yields:

$$\text{Integral } (WV)^2 dx = 3/16$$

(In particular, in (1): $-3/32 = \text{Integral } W^*W [V^*V/2 - egs^*egs + 2egs V]$ with $egs=.5$. We use $\text{Integral } W^*W V = .5 egs$. Note: W from (1) is not the same as the W we use although both are Gaussians. Their W is $B \exp(-.5x^2)$ while we use $W = B \exp(-.62x^2)$.)

Thus, one again obtains the roughly 20% correction in this approximation which we argue is not accurate.

We differ with (1) with respect to W and the perturbative potential and use the idea that one may solve the problem using different regions and applying the Schrodinger equation to the region near the classical turning point and extending to infinite. Thus, the perturbation integral is from a region between the classical turning points and no high x^4 enter into the equation.

As a result, a more accurate calculation should yield different results from (1). First, one should use $\exp(-.62x^2)$ and not $\exp(-.5x^2)$. Secondly, in the above we integrated $\int (WV)^2 dx$ from minus infinite to infinite when the range should be to the classical turning points or nearby where the Schrodinger equation takes over. For the example above with $m_0=k=1$, the turning points are ± 1 not at infinite. It seems this is about 1.4 standard deviations out. Thus, we argue that the more than 20% correction should be lowered.

Validity Conditions of Approximation

The method suggested in this note, uses the Schrodinger equation for the oscillator in the region near the classical turning points and extending to negative and positive infinite. For the ground state, it is known that $e=\sqrt{k/m}$ in such a case. For the nonperturbed equation near $x=0$ i.e. ((5)) we have the relationship

$$(E^2 - m_0^2) = Ek \quad \text{where } E=e+m_0 \quad ((6))$$

If e is to be constant for all x , this imposes some constraints.

For the nonrelativistic case of $e \ll m_0$ ((6)) becomes $2m_0 e = mk$ which is the nonrelativistic case. Consider e of the order of m_0 or even $e=m_0$. Then, in the Schrodinger region:

$$m_0 = \sqrt{k/m_0} \quad \text{or } k = m_0^3$$

In the relativistic region, ((6)) becomes:

$$9m_0^4 = 2m_0 k \quad \text{or } k \text{ is of the order } m_0^3$$

which is somewhat consistent with the nonrelativistic result with the exception of the factor $9/2$. For $e \gg m_0$ there is no such consistency, thus one must be careful in using this approximation for certain energy ranges.

Conclusion

It has been noted in the literature that there are problems using the Klein Godon equation $(E - .5kx^2)^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ because the x^4 term causes problems for large x . We argue that near classical turning points and extending to infinite, the Schrodinger equation may be used instead of the Klein-Gordon. In other words, there is no reason to worry about the x^4 term for large x as it does not appear in the Schrodinger case. The average kinetic energy is very low near the classical turning points and it seems there is no need to use relativistic equations in this region.

The relativistic equation may be used in regions near $x=0$ and in the region between the classical turning points. In such a case, the x^4 term becomes a perturbation term. In this note, we have carried out estimates for $m=1$ $k=1$ and show how to obtain results very similar to those of (1), but suggest that if the perturbation integral of the x^4 term is carried out numerically between the classical turning points and a $W=B\exp(-.62xx)$ instead of $B\exp(-.5xx)$ the correction of the method suggested here should be lower than that of (1).

References.

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2. Rao, N. and Kagali B. On the energy spectrum of the one dimensional Klein Gordon Equation <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0704.1869.pdf> (2004 or later)